

TECHNOLOGY OF TEACHING MATERIALS ON THE CONTENT LINE "STATISTICS AND PROBABILITY" IN VIII GRADES OF SECONDARY SCHOOLS

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Summary (Annotation). *The article draws attention to the elements that are considered necessary to be learned by students of the Mathematics subject "Statistics and Probability Content Line" taught in the VIII grades of general education schools, the fact that their educational activities are carried out in the direction of two basic standards (5.1 and 5.2), and presents the content and structured technological approach used to implement the educational process on the identified topics. The points that should be kept in focus in the process of teaching the topics are emphasized, it is considered appropriate to systematize the tasks according to the formulated research question, to have the students of the class work frontally and in groups (or pairs) to conduct research, and to conduct assessment in the lesson by levels.*

This paper presents a system of criteria and tasks that are considered acceptable for effective summative assessment.

Keywords: *mode, median and mean of data; test; probability; collection; selection; relatively complex events; compatible and incompatible events; scatterplot; centroid; greatest difference; cluster, gap, outlier; favorable cases; correlation; bar graph, two-column bar graph, pie chart, histogram, broken line graph.*

Relevance of the topic. It is known that the effectiveness of the activity of the educator and the learner in the real pedagogical process is conditioned by the methodological system formed and applied on the basis of a functional goal with a system-forming component. Since the formation of a methodological system is a project of the creative process (creative processes do not easily and once reveal their invariants), its improvement is an eternal didactic problem.

"Technology of teaching materials on the content line "Statistics and Probability" in the VIII grades of secondary schools" can be understood as the formation and application of a "methodological system" of teaching the said materials. Therefore, we perceive the presented research topic as a topical didactic problem.

Materials collected on the research topic interpretation of generalization. In the framework document of the Concept of General Education in the Republic of Azerbaijan (National Curriculum), the curriculum is defined as "a conceptual document that enables the effective organization, purposeful and consistent implementation of all activities related to the educational process", its content includes standards, expected results, necessary minimum, requirements for the preparation of learners, technology and assessment issues. In fact, each of these issues is included in the curriculum as its integral part, important components. The interaction of these components with each other, the completion of any one of them, its logical continuation are expected as an important requirement [1; 167]. There have been various approaches to modernizing the educational process, which have their own characteristics in terms of methodological systems. The elements of "Purpose \Leftrightarrow content \Leftrightarrow means \Leftrightarrow organizational form \Leftrightarrow result" were included in the structure of the educational system in different ways with their enabling functions, in other words, they entered the system corresponding to the changing content of the principles of education. Currently, in general education schools operating in Azerbaijan, preference is given to the active/interactive learning model and its methodological system (in other words, to the learner-centered implementation of education), which

is adequate to the adopted Curriculum for the implementation of education (For more information, see: [11-12].)

In mathematics, the “Statistics and Probability Content Line” was included in order for students to learn such issues as determining and calculating the average value of various numerical quantities, taking into account coincidences during selection, classifying collected materials, and conducting analysis on graphs. Through this content line, the study of issues such as performing probability experiments, collecting data, and graphically depicting them is ensured in elementary grades, and in higher grades, a foundation is created for a deeper study of statistics and its impact on daily life, and the formation of judgment and decision-making experience based on the collected data [6; 66-68].

A student who has completed his/her education in the 8th grade:

5.1. Collects, systematizes, analyzes statistical information and presents the results.

5.1.1. Formulates appropriate questions to collect the necessary statistical data.

5.1.2. Constructs a table or diagram that characterizes the change in data selected according to certain characteristics.

5.1.3. Finds the mode, median, and mean of collected numerical data.

5.1.4. Makes predictions based on data analysis.

5.2. Understands and applies the concepts of probability.

5.2.1. Determines the number of possible test outcomes.

5.2.2. Distinguishes between unlikely and likely events.

5.2.3. Finds the number of favorable cases in relatively complex events.

As can be seen, the educational activities of VIII grade students on the aforementioned content lines are carried out in the direction of two main standards - “Collects, systematizes, analyzes and presents statistical information” (5.1), “Understands and applies the concepts of probability” (5.2). The standards for mathematics cover the content that is important for all students within the general education course, describe the mathematical comprehension abilities, knowledge and skills of students, determine the issues that every student in the country can and should learn in the field of mathematics, and prepare students for the next stage of education.

Each standard objective includes several expected learning outcomes defined according to the levels of general education. As emphasized in scientific sources, in the content standard, knowledge and activity act as sides of the unit [3; 84-85].

The student can achieve the content he will master in mathematics through various activities. During his activity, he makes judgments to solve problems, proves mathematical propositions, correlates the information he has obtained, develops a general mathematical model and presents it in various ways. The indicated stages of student activity in the process of mastering the content ensure that the acquired knowledge and skills are more solid and long-lasting. Scientific sources correctly emphasize that the level of realization of the expected results of students' educational activities depends on the "dialectical unity of the educational situation (or tasks), educational operations, control and assessment elements". Educational activity is a type of human activity, a specific form of social activity of the individual, and training is an important characteristic of educational activity [2; 150].

The compilers of the mathematics curriculum and the authors of the textbook set are of the opinion that it is appropriate to implement the materials on the “Statistics and Probability Content Line” in the VIII grade on the following topics: Data collection; Data collection and presentation. Scatter diagram; Measures of central tendency and the largest difference; Probability calculation; Possible number of events; Dependent and independent events.

Based on scientific sources and our work experience, we consider it useful to apply the content and structured technological approach interpreted below in implementing the educational process on the topics in question:

1. Points to focus on in the methodological system of teaching the topic of "Data Collection".

The standard is formulated as follows: 5.1.2. Systematizes the collected data according to certain characteristics.

The teaching of the subject should create the basis for the realization of student skills, which are reflected in the following:

- ✘ Asks questions to gather information.
- ✘ In research, he explains the data that varies over a large range as a "population" and the part that is being researched as a "selection" based on the examples provided.
- ✘ It provides a collection and selection of examples for research.
- ✘ It justifies whether the prediction is correct or incorrect based on whether the choice for the collection is correct or incorrect.
- ✘ It makes predictions based on the results obtained from the research [7;116].

It is recommended to allocate 2 hours to teaching the topic. It is recommended to start teaching the topic by explaining the concepts of "collection" and "selection" as follows.

When the object under study has information that varies over a wide range, the study is conducted on small groups related to this object. Information that varies over a wide range is called a population (or population), and a small group selected from the population is called a sample. The results of the study conducted on the sample are applied to the population (population), a conclusion is drawn, and a prediction is made. For example, a teacher checked the notebooks of 3 students sitting in the first desks to check the level of homework completion. Here, the population is all the students in the class, and the sample is the 3 students sitting in the first desk. The selections can be random and systematic. The correct representation of the sample by the sample determines the quality of the study. In order for the students to understand what they are saying, the teacher draws their attention to two different cases. He addresses the students and says: "Let's examine in which of the following cases the sample really represents the population."

- To gather feedback on a new fragrance, store employees give customers a small bottle of perfume and ask for their opinions (an example of random sampling).

- One in five people entering a cafeteria during lunchtime is asked to complete a questionnaire designed to assess the quality of service (an example of systematic sampling) [4;1094].

In the next part of the lesson, students should work on assignments and acquire the skills of collecting and systematizing information. They should know that the steps involved in collecting and systematizing information are as follows:

Step 1 (Question formulation). At this stage, research is conducted on the formulation of the question, its sequence, and the nature of the possible answers.

Step 2 (Data collection). At this stage, answers are sought to the questions of when and where to collect information? How can the information be obtained (through a written questionnaire, oral survey, observation, experiment, etc.)? How should the information obtained be initially recorded?

Step 3 (Analysis, systematization and presentation of information). What type of graph should be chosen to present the information? Does the chosen form clearly show the answer to the question posed?

At this stage, you can benefit from the following task examples:

I. Which choice allows for a more accurate prediction about the object of research? Which is random, which is systematic?

1) A cafeteria, where the majority of customers are students, asks one out of every 15 students to stick pictures of their 4 favorite vegetables in a row on the wall.

2) A mark was placed on the order receipt of one in every 10 customers to check how many minutes customers sat in the dining room during lunch.

3) The opinions of the players of a football team were asked to determine the location of a new football field to be built.

4) The city council wants to find out whether people like taking dogs out for walks in parks. To do this, they asked 50 people who keep dogs at home.

II. Think of a research topic. Define the population and the sample. Write an example of both random and systematic sampling. Justify that your sampling is truly representative of the population [5; 1155].

2. Points to be focused on in the methodological system of teaching the topic "Collection and presentation of information. Scatter diagram".

The standard is formulated as follows: 5.1.2. Systematizes the collected data according to certain characteristics. 5.1.4. Determines the relationship between parameters in data with two parameters in simple cases.

The teaching of the subject should create the basis for the realization of student skills, which are reflected in the following:

- Presents the information given in the table by choosing an appropriate graphic form.
- Presents information given in a graphic form by selecting another graphic form.
- A diagram solves problems related to data presented graphically.
- It presents information in a table organized according to two parameters.
- It presents the data given according to two parameters in a table.
- It presents the data given by two parameters in a bar graph. [7;120]

It is recommended to allocate 5 hours to teaching the topic.

Choosing the right graphic form to present the collected data is very important. It is recommended to prepare a poster consisting of graphic forms that reflect the forms of presentation of data. These can be bar graphs, two-column bar graphs, pie charts, histograms, broken line graphs, etc.

The formation of students' skills in choosing a convenient form for presenting the collected information depends on their involvement in activities on appropriate tasks (see: Examples of such tasks are sufficiently presented in the materials Ibrahimov FN Methodology of Teaching Mathematics in Secondary Schools Based on the Curriculum Model (Baku: Mütərcim, 2016) and Ibrahimov FN Philosophy, Didactics, and Implementation Technology of Mathematical Education in Secondary Schools (Baku: Mütərcim, 2018)).

In the further continuation of the teaching process of the subject, it is advisable to use tasks that require theoretical and practical research, aimed at developing the intended skills in students, which are applied as a means of organizing whole-class or group work.

3. Points to be focused on in the methodological system of teaching the topic "Centric measures and the greatest difference".

The standard is formulated as follows: 5.1.3. Finds quantities that characterize the limits of variation of numerical data.

The teaching of the subject should create the basis for the realization of student skills, which are reflected in the following:

- It presents clusters, gaps, and outliers that fit the data.
- It uses measures of central tendency and greatest variance to analyze data.
- Makes judgments about the change in measures of central tendency and largest variance as new data is added or subtracted.

It is recommended to allocate 2 hours to teaching the topic.

The teaching of the topic can be started by involving students in research activities. In this process, the teacher brings these to the attention of students regarding measures of central tendency and the largest difference. He states that measures such as the numerical mean, mode, median and the largest difference are widely used in the analysis of statistical data. The numerical mean, mode, median are measures of central tendency. It is more convenient to use one or another of the statistical measures in the following cases:

- *In the absence of a sharp deviation from the numerical mean;*
- *From the median - in case of sharp deviations;*
- *From mode - when there is a large number of identical data;*
- *The biggest difference is when determining the interval of data change.*

At this point, it would be useful to suggest that students complete such an assignment.

Task. Justify the accuracy of the selected statistical indicators.

1) The ages of 6 people in a group are: 11, 14, 12, 12, 11, 32. Median.

2) Monthly income for 6 months (in manats): 325, 320, 300, 325, 325, 4000. Mode.

3) Samir's daily running distance (km) over 5 days: 3, 5, 4, 5, 6. Numerical average.

In the next part of the lesson, the following information about clusters, gaps, and outliers is brought to the attention of students. Data is sometimes collected in a small interval. This interval is called a cluster. An interval where there is no data is called a gap. Data that is too large or too small in numerical value than the available data is considered an outlier. It is important to show examples of these. For example, the teacher can create a visual basis for the explanation in the example of the scores collected by the students, thereby creating conditions for students to correctly understand the information.

In the further continuation of the teaching process of the subject, it is advisable to use tasks that require theoretical and practical research, aimed at developing the intended skills in students, which are applied as a means of organizing whole-class or group work.

3. Points to be focused on in the methodological system of teaching the topic of "Calculating Probability".

The standard is formulated as follows: 5.2.1. Understands the concepts of whether events are dependent or not, finds the probability of the product of two independent events. 5.2.2. Finds the probability of the product of two dependent events. 5.2.3. Applies the multiplication rule in problems related to calculating probabilities.

The teaching of the subject should create the basis for the realization of student skills, which are reflected in the following:

- Explains with examples his understanding of the concept of experimental and theoretical probability.

- It is understood that with the increase in the number of trials in the experimental probability, its value approaches the theoretical probability.

- Solves problems related to calculating theoretical and experimental probability and making predictions.

It is recommended to allocate 1 hour to teaching the topic. It is recommended to structure the teaching process of the topic according to the following scenario [7;132].

First, the concept of empirical probability is brought to the attention of students. The teacher explains that empirical probability is found on the basis of repeated trials of an experiment.

$$P(\text{event}) = \frac{\text{number of times a favorable event occurs}}{\text{the number of tests}}$$

Example 1. The bar graph shows the results of 50 dice rolls. What is the experimental probability of getting an odd number? [8; 206] The bar graph shows that 1 was rolled ten times, 3 was rolled five times, and 5 was rolled nine times. The number of favorable events is: $10+5+9=24$ times an odd number was rolled.

Number of tests: 50.

$$P(\text{odd number}) = \frac{24}{50} = \frac{12}{25}$$

The empirical probability of rolling an odd number is $\frac{12}{25}$, 0.48 or 48%.

Example 2. Empirical probability can be used to make predictions. In March, it was rainy on 2 of the last 10 days. If this trend continues, how many rainy days can we predict will be in April?

First, let's find the empirical probability determined by observation.

$$P(\text{rain}) = \frac{\text{number of occurrences of the event}}{\text{number of tests}} = \frac{\text{rainy days}}{\text{observation days}}$$

$$P(\text{rain}) = \frac{2}{10} = \frac{1}{5}$$

You can expect rain during the $30 \cdot \frac{1}{5} = 6$ day in April.

The teacher continues the lesson by giving students information about theoretical probability. He asks them who it is. $P(\text{event}) = \frac{\text{number of favorable cases}}{\text{number of possible cases}}$

The numerical value of the probability of a random event occurring varies in the interval from 0 to 1. Probability is expressed as a common fraction, decimal fraction, or percentage. The sum of the probability of an event occurring and the probability of its non-occurrence is equal to 1.

$$P(\text{occurrence}) + P(\text{non-occurrence}) = 1$$

The teacher presents an example to the students regarding the use of theoretical probability.

Example 3. The chance of winning 1000 manats when spinning the Charkhi-Felek board is $\frac{1}{10}$. If there are 1000 manats in 3 divisions on the board, how many divisions does the board have?

Solution: Let the total number of partitions be n .

$$P(\text{prize}) = \frac{\text{number of winning sections}}{\text{number of all parts}} = \frac{1}{10}; \frac{1}{10} = \frac{3}{n}; n = 30.$$

An example of comparing theoretical and experimental probability is considered.

Example 4. The bar graph shows the results of rolling a die 300 times. Find the probability of getting an odd number.

$$P(\text{odd number}) = \frac{\text{number of times odd numbers fall}}{\text{number of tests}} = \frac{148}{300} = \frac{37}{75} \approx 0,49$$

The teacher draws the students' attention to "Example 1" and suggests that they compare the experimental probabilities. It is concluded that as the number of trials increases, the experimental probability approaches the theoretical probability. When the number of trials is increased from 50 to 3000, the experimental probability also increases from 48% to 49%, approaching the theoretical probability of 50%.

4. Points that should be focused on in the methodological system of teaching the topic "Possible number of events".

The standard is formulated as follows: 5.2.3. Applies the multiplication rule in matters related to the calculation of probabilities.

The teaching of the subject should create the basis for the realization of student skills, which are reflected in the following:

- Finds the number of possible options in complex events using a branching diagram, without keeping a list, and using the multiplication rule.

It is recommended to allocate 1 hour to teaching the topic.

It is recommended to start the lesson by presenting the following information to the students. The teacher states that if an event is accompanied by the occurrence of one or more elementary events, these events are called complex events. For example, tossing two coins at the same time is a complex event. The number of possible cases in complex events can be found: 1) using a branching diagram; 2) without keeping a list; 3) using a table; 4) using the multiplication rule. In the process of teaching the topic, special attention is paid to mastering the multiplication principle, which is formulated as follows.

Multiplication principle. If it is possible to choose an element a in n ways and for each such choice, it is possible to choose an element b in m ways, then it is possible to choose the pair (a, b) in $n \cdot m$ ways.

In order for students to better grasp the presented principle, they are involved in activities on specially selected examples [see: 5 and 9].

Example 1 (By constructing a table). The number of possible events when a die and a coin are thrown together: 12 events. According to the multiplication principle: 2 events ($m = 2$) (are possible with a coin, and 6 events are possible with a die. ($n = 6$))

Number of possible events: $2 \cdot 6 = 12$ [5; 1165]

Example 2 (By constructing a branching diagram.) Number of possible events when tossing three coins: 8

According to the multiplication rule 2 events with each metal coin.

Number of possible events: $2 \cdot 2 \cdot 2 = 8$ [9; 210]

In the further continuation of the teaching process of the subject, it is advisable to use tasks that require theoretical and practical research, aimed at developing the intended skills in students, which are applied as a means of organizing whole-class or group work.

4. Points to be focused on in the methodological system of teaching the topic "Dependent and Independent Events".

The standard is formulated as follows: 5.2.1. Understands the concepts of whether events are dependent or not, finds the probability of the product of two independent events. 5.2.2. Finds the probability of the product of two dependent events. 5.2.3. Applies the multiplication rule in problems related to calculating probabilities [8; 211].

The teaching of the subject should create the basis for the realization of student skills, which are reflected in the following:

- Distinguishes between dependent and independent events.
- Calculates possible variants of dependent and independent events using the multiplication principle.
- Solves problems related to the probability of dependent and independent events.

It is recommended to allocate 2 hours to teaching the topic. During the lesson, students will perform two consecutive experiments visually.

Experiment 1. The teacher says that there are 2 red balls and 1 yellow ball in a bag. Imagine that you have to draw two balls from the bag in succession. Record the color of each ball you draw and put the ball back in the bag. Create a branching diagram to find the number of possible events by writing the colors with the first letter of the letter and complete it. Find the probability of drawing a red ball in succession.

Does the color of the ball that comes out in the second toss depend on the color of the ball that comes out in the first toss? Students' opinions are listened to.

Before conducting the second experiment, students are introduced to the following information about independent events.

If the occurrence of one event does not affect the probability of the occurrence of another event, such events are called independent events. For example, when a die and a coin are thrown at the same time, the outcome of the die does not depend on whether the coin lands heads or tails. The probability of two or more independent events is equal to the product of the probabilities of these events:

It is also written as the formula. $P(A \text{ and } B) = P(A) \cdot P(B)$; $P(A \cap B) = P(A) \cdot P(B)$

For three independent events by a similar rule [7;136-137]:

$$P(A, B \text{ and } C) = P(A) \cdot P(B) \cdot P(C)$$

Experiment 2. The teacher presents the experiment to the students as follows: Imagine that there are still 2 red and 1 yellow balls in the bag. You take one ball out of the bag each time and note its color, but do not put the ball back in the bag. Complete the branching diagram to find the number of possible elementary events by noting the first letter of the colors. Find the probability of getting a

red ball in a row. Does the color of the ball drawn in the second toss depend on the color of the ball drawn in the first toss?

Students' opinions are listened to. The teacher brings to the attention of students the information presented below regarding the dependent events and incidents.

If the occurrence of one event affects the possibility of another event occurring, these events are called dependent events.

For example, if 10 out of 100 cards in a bag are free, then one person's drawing of a free card on the first try affects the other person's drawing of a free card. The probability of two dependent events A and B is equal to the product of the probability of event A and the probability of event B occurring after event A occurs.

$$P(A \text{ and } B) = P(A) \cdot P(\text{the occurrence of event } B \text{ after event } A).$$

In order for students to better assimilate the material presented on independent and dependent events, they are involved in activities on specially selected examples.

Example 1 (Independent event). A coin and a die are thrown together. Calculate the probability that the coin lands heads and the die lands heads.

The probability of getting a prime number (2,3,5) when rolling a dice is: $P(\text{map}) = \frac{1}{2}$;

$$P(\text{prime}) = \frac{3}{6} = \frac{1}{2};$$

$$P(\text{map and prime}) = \frac{1}{2} \cdot \frac{1}{2} = \frac{1}{4};$$

The probability of getting a map and a prime number is $\frac{1}{4}$, 0,25 or 25%

Example 2 (Dependent event). Players for a TV show are randomly selected from 100 viewers. 5 of Teymur's relatives and 9 of his classmates are watching the show in the studio. What is the probability that one of Teymur's relatives is selected in the first choice and one of his classmates in the second choice? The probability of the relatives being selected in the first choice is:

$$P(\text{relative}) = \frac{5}{100} = \frac{1}{20};$$

The probability of his friends choosing the second option:

$$P(\text{friend after relative}) = \frac{9}{99} = \frac{1}{11};$$

Using the formula for calculating the probability of two dependent events, we can calculate the probability of Teymur's relative and classmate being called first among those selected in succession.

$$P(\text{relative after friend}) = P(\text{relative}) \cdot P(\text{friend after relative})$$

$$P(\text{relative and friend}) = \frac{1}{20} \cdot \frac{1}{11} = \frac{1}{220}.$$

In the further continuation of the teaching process of the subject, it is advisable to use tasks that require theoretical and practical research, aimed at developing the intended skills in students, which are applied as a means of organizing whole-class or group work.

It is advisable to take advantage of the small summative assessment criteria and task types listed below.

Small summative assessment criteria:

1. Asks questions to gather information.
2. Chooses a method to collect information.
3. Makes predictions based on the information obtained.
4. Solves problems based on graphically presented data.
5. Uses a line graph to visually visualize the frequency of data.
6. It makes judgments about the change in central tendency measures and the largest variance as new data is added or subtracted.
7. Solves problems based on theoretical and experimental probability calculations and forecasting.
8. It presents possible variants of dependent and independent events with a branching diagram.

9. Calculates possible variants of dependent and independent events using the multiplication rule.

10. Solves problems of calculating the probability of dependent and independent events.

Small summative assessment tasks:

1) The faces of the cube are colored green, yellow, and red. The cube was rolled 10 times and the result was as shown in the table below. How many faces of the cube would be more accurate to think of as yellow?500

Colors	Green	Yellow	Red
Number	90	370	40

- A) 1 B) 2 C) 3 D) 4

2) During his research, Javid wants to find out which color of car buyers prefer the most. It turned out that buyers prefer white cars more. Which measure would be more accurate if Javid used to present his information?

- A) median B) mode C) numerical mean D) largest difference

3) There are chocolate-covered lemon, milk, and strawberry candies in a glass jar. Shamkhal ate two of the candies. Both were milky. If Shamkhal wanted to eat two more candies, what expression can be used to find the probability that both of them will be milky?101010

- A) $\frac{1}{10} \cdot \frac{1}{10}$ B) $\frac{9}{30} \cdot \frac{8}{28}$ C) $\frac{8}{28} \cdot \frac{7}{27}$ D) $\frac{7}{20} \cdot \frac{6}{21}$

4) There are 30 students in a class. If one student is selected from the class, the probability that he/she is an excellent student is $\frac{2}{3}$. How many excellent students are there in this class?

- A) 10 B) 15 C) 20 D) 5

5) The table shows the relationship between the scores students earn on the scoring system and the amount of time (in hours) they spend watching TV after school. Draw a scatter diagram for this relationship.

TV viewing time (in hours)	Points earned	TV viewing time (in hours)	Points earned
1	87	5	52
1.5	89	0.5	92
3	72	2	85
2	71	4	68
3	65	2.5	79

6) Systematize the given data starting from the 51 – 60 interval and construct a histogram.
 56, 68, 73, 79, 82, 82, 83, 85, 87, 88, 89, 90, 90, 91, 93, 95, 100

7) There are 4 white and 5 green balls in a box. 2 balls are removed by putting them back in the box. Find the probability that both balls removed are white.

Scientific novelty of the research work. The argument that determines the optimality of the methodological system of teaching training materials and the way to incorporate this argument into the activities of the educator are shown.

Practical significance of the research work. The inclusion of the argument that the methodological system of teaching materials is optimal in the activities of the educator has a positive impact on the effectiveness of his work.

Result. 1) The optimality of the methodological system of teaching materials on the content line “Statistics and Probability” in the VIII grades of secondary schools depends on the dialectical unity of its components “opportunity→action→new quality”, the said dialectics determines the level of realization of the “paradigm” of the educational process; 2) a reliable way to form the components of the methodological system of teaching learning materials in a dialectical unity: (goal⇔content⇔means⇔method⇔organizational form⇔result) is a “system-structural approach” based on the “idea of system analysis” to the educational process.

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